

AQUASERV

Research services
for **sustainable aquaculture,**
fisheries and **blue economy**

Deliverable D3.1 - AQUASERV DMP

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Executive Summary

This is the first version of the Data Management Plan for AQUASERV, created for the deliverable D3.1. This document outlines how the data collected or generated within AQUASERV is expected to be handled during and after the end of the project by the service providers and the participants of the Transnational Access (TA) programme. This DMP builds on that of [ASSEMBLE Plus](#) and incorporates best practices at the national, EU, and international levels, and recommendations and guidance from the ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS), Research Data Alliance (RDA), and the International Oceanographic Data Exchange (IODE). This DMP outlines the methodologies and standards that can be applied to AQUASERV data, whether and how the data can be shared and/or made open, and how the data should be curated and preserved. This first version of the DMP will be added to as AQUASERV as its TA programme proceeds.

1. Introduction

1.1. The AQUASERV project

AQUASERV – RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE, FISHERIES AND THE BLUE ECONOMY

The AQUASERV project is a five-year initiative running from April 2024 to March 2029, funded by the European Union. The project aims to provide research services that support sustainable aquaculture, fisheries, and the blue economy. AQUASERV involves collaboration among 40 partners across Europe and is aligned with the goals of the HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01 call, which focuses on RI services to enable research and innovation (R&I) to address key challenges and EU priorities.

The overarching objectives of AQUASERV are to enhance, integrate, and customise research infrastructures (RI) capacities (including facilities, instruments, and expertise) and through the provision of transnational access (on-site or remote) and virtual access, to significantly further scientific knowledge and promote and facilitate the implementation of European Common Fisheries Policy, the Farm to Fork Strategy, the Sustainable Blue Economy, and the [European Green Deal](#).

AQUASERV will achieve these objectives by offering scientists from academia and business industry remote and on-site transnational (TA) and virtual (VA) access to services from an advanced set of European RIs related to research and management of marine and freshwater biological resources, food, and biotechnology. These RIs include the The International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC), Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems (AnaEE-ERIC), AQUAEXCEL, Infrastructure for Promoting Metrology in Food and Nutrition (METROFOOD-RI), and European Aquaculture Society (EAS) which is both a service provider and

stakeholder. AQUASERV also includes the RI for European Research Infrastructure for Science, technology, and Innovation policy Studies (RISIS) to garner contributions from the social sciences and aid the translation of results to policymakers thereby enhancing the societal impact of the project.

1.2 The AQUASERV Data Collection

The data collected by AQUASERV TA programme will reflect the diverse range of topics addressed within the project. Each WP will produce their own data throughout the project's lifetime (see Table 1, Annex). While the DMP will mostly concern the work of the TA users, it needs to also cover all the data produced by the project. This will include any data gathered while creating any outcomes of the project through other WPs:

This diversity requires tailored approaches to data management to ensure that all datasets meet the project's standards and objectives. AQUASERV provides a comprehensive suite of services, including advanced imaging, biobanks, structural and chemical analysis, data analysis and software support, culture collections, molecular biology and omics, aquaria and tanks, dry laboratories, taxonomic services, marine model organisms, climate-controlled rooms, and coastal research vessels with scientific diving capabilities. Data produced by these services will include raw data, curated (partially-processed) data products, and final reports, publications, and models. Most of the data generated from TA projects will be managed following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. The outputs (data, publications) will adhere to the principle of being "as open as possible and as closed as necessary," ensuring that data is accessible while respecting necessary restrictions. In this DMP, we will detail the strategies and procedures employed to manage the TA data in alignment with these requirements.

The type of data that will be collected by the TA projects cannot be known *a-priori*. Because the AQUASERV consortium is diverse in research topics, the range of data formats and types that will be generated are also necessarily diverse. However, since the projects will be carried out at the AQUASERV partner aquatic stations, in-house expertise will be provided to the visiting researchers so that they can conform to standard procedures and norms of the AQUASERV data collection. Based on our experience with the data collected by the TA projects within ASSEMBLE PLUS (grant agreement number 730984) and Assemble Marine project (grant agreement number 227799), most datasets are provided as spreadsheets, images, and variously-formatted text files. Consolidation of these data types is a priority of the data management activities of AQUASERV, particularly within thematic research fields. Standardisation at the data level will be achieved by applying community-based standards as proposed by international initiatives, such as the International Oceanographic Data Exchange Programme (IODE), the Ocean

Biogeographic Information System (OBIS), the Genomics Standards Consortium (GSC), and the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).

Different data types are often published in different file formats. Table 2 gives an overview of possible file formats for sharing, re-use and preservation (based on the UK Data Archive). AQUASERV recommends avoiding the use of proprietary software formats when possible. If data files are in a proprietary or obscure (non-community standard) format, it is recommended that the data be converted to a more common data format. More details on the specific file formats used for the thematic data types produced in AQUASERV is given in Sec. 2.3.1.

In addition to the TA data – which forms the larger part of the AQUASERV data collection – there will be outputs from the other WPs in the project. Most of these will be in the form of deliverables, publications, communications material, etc, and these will be made open access in the usual manner: this DMP will address these outputs as well, as they are produced.

1.3 The AQUASERV Data Origins and Scope

Data within the TA programme of the AQUASERV project originate from the aquatic stations that form the AQUASERV consortium. TA projects are research activities offered to, and carried out by, visiting researchers operating under the umbrella of AQUASERV. The origin of the TA data will be the scientific project run by the visiting researcher, and the range of topics covered will be broad. The datasets are mostly limited in scope because they are gathered during relatively short (< one month) experiments with a single focus.

From our experience in AssemblePlus and Assemble Marine, many of the TA projects are a part of PhD and postdoc projects, are smaller parts of larger programmes, are trials of methods or experiments to come. As such, data sets are often limited in scope and not too large, and are often part of larger data sets collected outside of AQUASERV, but within this DMP we will only focus on the data collected within the TA programme of AQUASERV.

It is of prime importance that the TA data are [FAIR](#) (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and are as open as possible, certainly open by default. Within this DMP we will outline how this can be done; within WP3 we will assist and train the AQUASERV partners and the TA users on how to do this.

For the outputs arising from the other WPs in AQUASERV, the origin will be the work that each WP will carry out.

1.4 Other users of AQUASERV data

The AQUASERV consortium encompasses a broad range of scientific disciplines which use a broad range of instrumentation and activities which in turn produce a broad range of data types. The services offered under AQUASERV include various types of sampling, processing, and experimental instrumentation and activities (cryobanking, genomics, photogrammetry, etc), access to biological resources, and e-services, all of which collectively support ecosystem access and research activities.

The data will be of use to the wider aquatic scientific community, beyond the research project under which they will be collected. Possible applications for the AQUASERV data are in theoretical and applied research in many aquatic science disciplines, such as ecology and aquaculture, plus applications to broader domains such as policy support, conservation, blue technology, food safety, and pharmaceutical research, among many others. Application sectors could include gene and cell engineering (molecular farming, cell factories), bio-refineries, biostatistics, software development, subsea industries, nutrition, medicine and health care, aquaculture, environmental remediation, and bioenergy and biomaterials. Other potential users of the data include Marine Protected Areas agencies and Marine Scientific boards.

The AQUASERV public web pages will include communications to the general public, based on the work carried out within the consortium, and this will also have pedagogical uses.

1.5 The Transnational Access (TA) DMP

As part of the application process from TA Call 1 onwards, some basic data management questions will be asked. The main aim of these questions is to alert applicants on the requirements that data produced during TA projects should be archived and catalogued, should be made Open Access as soon as possible after data collection, and that any eventual refereed publications should be Open Access publications.

“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”

[- Open science. \(n.d.\). European Research Executive Agency](#)

Before a TA visit is started, the user will be asked to begin on a data management plan using a template provided via the AQUASERV website. This template will be based on Horizon2020 DMPs, addressing the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable points, but will have a concise version with suggested answers (many TA users have little experience with data management). A guide to FAIR data management

for TA users will also be provided on the AQUASERV website. TA users will be requested to archive their data and catalogue them; assistance in these steps will be provided by WP3.

2. FAIR Data

FAIR data principles are to ensure that data are:

- **Findable:** Data should be stored in a community repository with a metadata record created in a publicly accessible data catalogue, which is often part of the repository. Both data and metadata must have a unique and persistent identifier to ensure they can always be located.
- **Accessible:** Metadata must be publicly accessible and available for machine-to-machine interactions. Access to the metadata should be maintained even if the data themselves become unavailable.
- **Interoperable:** Data and metadata should be formatted using standard formats and vocabularies to facilitate compatibility and integration across different systems.
- **Re-usable:** The terms for re-use should be clearly defined, typically through licensing. Metadata records must include information about the provenance of the data.

An explanation of FAIR data management, and our expectations for Open Access data and publications, will be found on the FAIR data management pages of the AQUASERV site. These explanations and instructions will be focussed on the creators of the TA users.

2.1. Making data findable

2.1.1. Data

Data generated from AQUASERV activities will be made findable. For those outputs generated by the WPs of AQUASERV this will be via the AQUASERV website. For data arising from the TA projects, the data will be required to be archived in community repositories and given a metadata description in a data catalogue. A list of suitable repositories and catalogues for different data types/disciplines will be provided to TA users. Links between the data and scientific publications will be encouraged, to enhance the findability of both.

2.1.2. Metadata

Metadata is provided to describe data and make them findable (e.g., via a data catalogue). Within this DMP we will explain metadata to the TA applicants and provide recommendations on the metadata for

datasets of different disciplines and types. These recommendations will be provided via the AQUASERV website and the FAIR data training materials to be produced in 2025.

2.1.3. File naming

Structured data storage is essential for proper and secure storage of data files and records. For any file-based storage, this includes unambiguous file naming, the use of proper versioning, and a clear and intuitive folder structure. The use of a standard file naming convention per data type, and a clear versioning will be encouraged by AQUASERV, and in some cases is ensured by the use of community services such as ELIXIR (the European Life-sciences Infrastructure for Biological Information) and OBIS. Moreover, the use of a relational database system to store those data where there is a repeated need for entry, storage, querying and analysis will be encouraged. Specific systems are available to support the information management of certain lab and field workflows. These LIMS (Laboratory Information Management Systems) and FIMS (Field Information Management Systems) have predefined data models and interfaces that can facilitate a lot of the repeating processes in the research environment.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

The AQUASERV data policy is primarily based on the EMBRC data policy, which covers all of the FAIR aspects including access. The EMBRC-ERIC Data Policy builds on the general principles described by the EMBRC-ERIC Statutes and the EMBRC Technical and Scientific Description for research data.

2.2.1. The AQUASERV's Data Policy

This section outlines the data policy framework guiding the collection, storage, use, and sharing of data throughout this project. The policy aims to ensure data integrity while ensuring personal privacy for the data collector. By adhering to the following principles, the policy ensures the responsible handling of data. Additional information on the uses of personal and digital data collected from project users and stakeholders on the AQUASERV can be found on the [privacy policy](#) page.

Main points:

- All data generated during a TA project must be published in open, community-driven, repositories or data catalogues
- Data should be openly published with a [Creative Common CC-BY 4.0 licence](#)
- Written reports and publications resulting from the project should be Open Access, which can be achieved by publishing in open access journals, or by making publications freely available via an open access repository ([further information can be found here](#))

- Data should be published in formats that are open community standards and machine interoperable, and be accompanied by sufficient metadata to ensure they are reusable

2.2.2. Open Access

Following the [guidelines](#) of Open Science in Horizon, all data collected or produced within the AQUASERV consortium will by default be open (freely distributed in appropriate repositories); exceptions will be allowed:

1. Data that are subject to intellectual property rights
2. Data that include sensitive information (e.g. rare species or environments, in which case a partial data release may be possible)
3. Data that are embargoed until scientific publication (with a maximum wait time of 24 months, unless extended for a reason other than the timing of scientific publication)
4. If prompt data publication jeopardises the project's goals (with the reason being unrelated to the timing of scientific publication)

We note that partners of the project are obligated to comply with open access requirements; we advocate this also for all Transnational Access (TA) users.

Each request for an exception will be considered with due diligence, however, it is the responsibility of the TA researcher to conform with these requirements, AQUASERV will not act as an enforcer.

Nonetheless, failure to follow the guidelines will be taken into consideration in future application for TA access.

2.2.3. Storage

The storage of data created by the research activities carried out in the AQUASERV aquatic stations during TA activities will primarily be the responsibility of the TA users, and in some cases also that of the AQUASERV stations. However, the aim is that all AQUASERV data will be published in community-specific repositories when possible. To stimulate discovery and re-use of the data, AQUASERV will also help the TA scientists to maximally exploit existing data-flow pathways to share data through European e-infrastructures such as EMODnet, LifeWatch and ELIXIR, and global initiatives such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS), especially its biodiversity component (GEOBON). In this way, the data have the best possible guarantee of long-term storage, findability and accessibility. Table 4 (Annex) lists some potential (European and non-European) data repositories for redistribution for the thematic data types generated within AQUASERV, for TA data.

2.2.4. Data Access

Data access will usually be guaranteed by the data repository/catalogue where the data are stored and made findable. In addition to these, general repositories such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>, which also links to GitHub) and national repositories may be used. For the cases where access to the data needs to be restricted, this can be identified at the time the data is submitted to the data repository. For much of the data expected to be produced by the AQUASERV TA users, the data will be of formats that can be handled by commonly-used commercial or open software (e.g. they are spreadsheets and images). Well-established routines are available for genomics data (e.g. ELIXIR). Data that are produced by community-standard software systems will be accessible to those using the same, community-standard, software.

2.3. Making data interoperable

AQUASERV realises that common data and metadata standards and formats are key aspects of technological and semantic data operability. Standardisation makes the data discoverable and practically usable and this way promotes international and interdisciplinary access to, and use of, research data. To ensure correct and proper use and interpretation of the AQUASERV data by the owners and re-users, the use of standardised vocabularies and ontologies is also necessary.

2.3.1. File formatting

The format and software in which research data are created depend on how researchers choose to collect and analyse data, often determined by discipline-specific standards and customs. Ensuring the long-term usability of the AQUASERV data requires consideration of the most appropriate software and file formats. Table 5 (Annex) lists some file formats, broken down by thematic data type, that can be used in the AQUASERV consortium.

Given the broad spectrum of data types, there is a large offer of domain-specific formats for data sharing and thematic systems that can serve redistribution of those data.

2.3.2. Data formatting and vocabulary standards

Standardisation at the data level will be performed by applying community-based standards as proposed by international initiatives such as the International Oceanographic Data Exchange Programme (IODE), the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS), the Genomics Standards Consortium (GSC) and the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).

Data standards are often specific to the discipline/instrument that is producing the data. WP3 will provide more detailed recommendations on FAIR and open data standards that will be published on the AQUASERV website and WP3 FAIR training material.

A FAIR controlled vocabulary is designed to enhance human and machine understanding of terms by ensuring each term has unique and persistent identifiers (PIDs) from the outset. These terms are web-accessible, with versioning and change information readily available. Ideally, a FAIR vocabulary also supports multiple languages. The use of such controlled vocabularies ensures that every term is unambiguous, making it easily understandable for humans and more accessible to machines. Moreover, when terms are machine-readable, it enhances interoperability, allowing machines not only to read but also to interpret the terms. Some controlled vocabularies are listed in Table 3 (Annex), these are particularly useful to use in (meta)data as keywords, measurements/parameters, descriptions of experimental instruments, and terms related to habitat, materials, environmental context, taxonomy, and geography.

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1. Quality control

For AQUASERV TA research data, the quality control of the data can happen at various stages during the data collection and processing. An initial quality control is needed at the local level and early in the collection process. Additional controls will take place at a later stage of the data life cycle. Description of the QC stages is expected to be included in the TA DMPs.

The initial quality control of the data, during data collection, is the primary responsibility of the AQUASERV data creator/owner, who must ensure that the recorded data reflect the facts, responses, observations and events. The quality of the data collection methods used strongly influences data quality, and documenting in detail how data are collected provides evidence of such quality. Errors can also occur during data entry. Data are digitised, transcribed, entered in a database or spreadsheet, or coded. Here, quality is ensured by standardised and consistent procedures for data entry with clear instructions. Quality control is the responsibility of the data collector and is not subject to this DMP.

2.4.2. Long term re-use

AQUASERV supports the concept of FAIR data and will help TA users and the AQUASERV marine station and lagoon in making their research data FAIR. The decision about long-term provision will be taken as the

data are stored. Any necessary discussion for particular datasets (for example, particularly large datasets, IPR-sensitive datasets) will involve the AQUASERV data management and the data producer. Embargo or opt-outs from open access are outlined in Sec. 2.2.2. The long-term reuse of most data is provided in terms of access rights.

There are no plans to end the provision of the AQUASERV data, and they should therefore be available for re-use for as long as the repositories used exist.

2.4.3. Provenance

Provenance is about providing trustability, traceability, and reusability of data: by describing the who, how/what, where, and when of the steps that led to the published data, you are providing the transparency required for trustability, the details required for traceability, and the information required for data re-use.

The prime provenance metadata are about the

- Protocols for collecting, processing, and storing physical material, and the instruments used
- Software for processing digital data
- Links backwards to the provenance and origin of any source material or data used
- Agents who performed distinct tasks
- Spatial and temporal ranges
- Update information (versions, update reasons)

Provenance is often not fully accounted for in the standard metadata forms that the data creators fill in for their chosen data publisher in the marine data world. This is largely because standard practices in collecting the necessary metadata and organising them into a provenance-metadata package, are lacking. Within the AQUASERV project we will address this through the provision of training and templates, and links to these will be included in this DMP when ready.

3. Allocation of Resources

3.1. Costs for making data FAIR

Resources for long-term preservation of datasets will be ensured by their storage in repositories such as those outlined in Table 4, and this is the responsibility of the TA scientists. Where the stations in which the research was carried out normally archive data taken with their instruments anyway, the costs for storing those data will be borne locally. The costs for making publications open access can vary from 500

to 5000 euros, depending on the journal. The project will not provide direct funding to TA users for this. However, numerous agreements now exist between national funding agencies, universities, and publishers, which should mitigate any issues. Additionally, green open access is available as an option. For the WPs, if a budget has been allocated, it can be utilised accordingly. Additionally, the European Commission offers a free open-access publication platform, [Open Research Europe](#).

3.2. Responsibilities

Implementation of the DMP is necessary at both the central and local levels. The coordination of the AQUASERV DMP and each TA DMP lies with the AQUASERV WP3. The local service providers will be trained to ensure the DMP is implemented at their local level (i.e. within their labs/stations/service providers) so that they can then help the TA users with their responsibility for their own TA-linked DMPs. WP3 will oversee compliance, and will also support the (local and TA) service providers by organising the necessary training.

The requirement to create a DMP and make data FAIR and open is made clear during the TA application process.

The responsibilities of service providers for several steps in the data management process are summarised here:

- AQUASERV (WP3) will advise and train its partners to organise structured, accessible storage of data and the necessary metadata.
- Quality control of the data is primarily the joint responsibility of the AQUASERV TA users and the aquatic station/lab/ service providers. AQUASERV will organise training in quality assurance processes for its service providers, for the various types of data.
- Each AQUASERV TA user will describe their generated datasets in a data catalogue and link to that archived data for open access. The metadata in the catalogue record must describe the scientific and the technical aspects of the data, and ideally provide reusability via provenance information.
- In general, the responsibility for ensuring adequate storage capacity during the TA access lies primarily with the AQUASERV service providers. AQUASERV will engage in mapping the needs of the service providers to use European and international repositories.
- The responsibility for backup and recovery of the data also lies primarily with the AQUASERV service providers, and with the repositories chosen by the TA users as included within those repositories' own data policies.

- AQUASERV will ensure compliance with the EU regulations regarding the protection of personal data (<http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/>).
- AQUASERV will promote a culture of openness and sharing of data and will therefore stimulate the exchange of good practices in data access and sharing by liaising with existing European initiatives or relevance for environmental and biological data and bioinformatics.

4. Data Security

AQUASERV will undertake all required efforts needed to protect the data, products and services against unauthorised use. The primary responsibility to take necessary measures to ensure data security lies with the service providers, and once stored in a community data repository the security provisions come from there.

Physical security, network security and security of computer systems and files all need to be considered to ensure the security of data and prevent unauthorised access, changes to data, disclosure or destruction of data.

5. Ethical Aspects

AQUASERV will be compliant with the EMBRC ethics review guidelines. Furthermore, AQUASERV will take measures to be compliant with the EU regulations regarding the protection of personal data (<http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/>). An AQUASERVs ethics checklist, which is also a required submission for the project at this 6-month point, can be consulted for further information.

6. Next Versions of the DMP

This DMP is a living document and will be updated throughout the course of the project. In year one, WP3 is engaged in a landscaping of the data that will be produced at the partner aquatic stations of AQUASERV in the TA programme. The year two DMP will contain updates taken from this work.

Annex

Table 1. Overview of the outputs expected to be produced by each WP through the AQUASERV lifetime.

Work Package	Types	Destination	Open Access
WP1	Guidelines, Reports, Handbooks, mailing lists for communication and dissemination, Data Management Plans, Permits and Authorizations for projects, catalogue of services	Deliverables are submitted on the European Union Platform Sygma and Zenodo, that creates a doi	Access follows what is established during the workplan, whether available for the consortium or open to all
WP2	Branding: visual ID, templates, print material	Internal use of the project, available for members at the EMDESK platform	
WP2	Digital communications: videos, website content, digital content	Social media platforms, website, Zenodo	Restricted access to members, and on the EMDESK project platform
WP2	Strategic communication: A Communication, Dissemination and Outreach Plan defining the strategy that the AQUASERV project will implement	Zenodo	Restricted access to members, and on the EMDESK project platform
WP3	Survey of service providers and their data types	EMDESK and googledrive	Public (summary of the survey)

WP3	Training material	OceanTraining and website	Access controlled, but open access otherwise
WP3	AQUASERV Internal call applications	EMDESK	Private, but summarised in Public deliverables
WP3	DMP and Landscaping reports	EMDESK, googledrive	Public
WP4	Publications	Zenodo	Public
	Database of stakeholders, access results	Website	Access controlled, publicly available (unless IP protection and/or TA/VA agreement requires embargo)
WP4	TNA success stories	Website	Public
WP5	Registration for the training courses	Internal use of the project	Sensitive
WP5	Training courses	Online	Access controlled, but open access otherwise
WP6	Roadmaps as leaflet	Website, social media, Zenodo	Public
WP6	Reports	<i>See grant agreement</i>	<i>See grant agreement</i>
WP6	Back casting – study	Scientific journal, Zenodo	Public
WP7	Catalogue of the services of our access providers (partners in the TA programme)		Public

WP7	Data on applicants' profile (e.g. gender, career status, home institute, nationality)	Internal use only	Sensitive
WP7	Data on applicant projects (access provider chosen, scientific project to be carried out, number of team members, etc.)	Internal use only	Sensitive
WP7	Data on the feedback of the TA users (on-site, remote and virtual) programme	Internal use only	Sensitive
WP7	Data on the feedback of our access managers on the TA programme	Internal use only	Sensitive
WP7	Data on the use of installations (type of access and "unit of access" delivered)	European Commission	
WP7	Data on the feedback of reviewers of TA applications	Internal use only	Sensitive

Table 2. Overview of the possible data file formats used for sharing, re-use, and preservation (based on the [UK Data Archive](#)).

Type of data	Acceptable formats for sharing, re-use, and preservation	Other acceptable formats for data preservation
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<p>Quantitative tabular data with extensive metadata. A dataset with variable labels, code labels, and defined missing values, in addition to the matrix of data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPSS portable format (.por) • Delimited text and command ('setup') file (SPSS, Stata, SAS, etc.) containing metadata information • Some structured text or mark-up file containing metadata information, e.g. DDI XML file 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proprietary formats of statistical packages e.g. SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta) • MS Access (.mdb/.accdb)
<p>Omics data. Data arising from omics-based studies are found in a wide variety of formats. Some of the more common formats are used to disseminate sequence data, sequence fragments, sequence comparisons, sequence annotations, and sequence alignments.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FASTA/FASTQ are text-based formats that contain sequence data, sequences along with, and without, their corresponding quality scores, typically generated from high-throughput sequencing platforms. • BAM/SAM binary and text based sequence alignment formats • GFF/GTF, GBK are text based sequence annotation formats • VCF a text-based sequence variation format 	

<p>Quantitative tabular data with minimal metadata. A matrix of data with or without column headings or variable names, but no other metadata or labelling</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comma-separated values (CSV) file (.csv) • Tab-delimited file (.tab) • Including delimited text of given character set with SQL data definition statements where appropriate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delimited text of given character set - only characters not present in the data should be used as delimiters (.txt) • Widely-used formats, e.g. MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), MS Access (.mdb/.accdb), dBase (.dbf) and OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods)
<p>Geospatial data. Vector and raster data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESRI Shapefile (essential - .shp, .shx, .dbf, optional - .prj, .sbx, .sbn) • geo-referenced TIFF (.tif, .tfw) • CAD data (.dwg) • tabular GIS attribute data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESRI Geodatabase format (.mdb) • MapInfo Interchange Format (.mif) for vector data • Keyhole Mark-up Language (KML) (.kml) • Adobe Illustrator (.ai), CAD data (.dxf or .svg) • binary formats of GIS and CAD packages
<p>Qualitative data. Textua</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • eXtensible Mark-up Language (XML) text according to an appropriate Document Type Definition (DTD) or schema (.xml) • Rich Text Format (.rtf) • plain text data, ASCII (.txt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypertext Mark-up Language (HTML) (.html) • widely-used proprietary formats, e.g. MS Word (.doc/.docx) • some proprietary/software-specific formats, e.g.

		<p>NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti</p>
<p>Digital image data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TIFF version 6 uncompressed (.tif) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg) but only if created in this format • TIFF (other versions) (.tif, .tiff) • Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF) (.pdf) • standard RAW image format (.raw) • Photoshop files (.psd)
<p>Digital audio data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free Lossless Audio Codec (FLAC) (.flac) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPEG-1 Audio Layer 3 (.mp3) but only if created in this format • Audio Interchange File Format (AIFF) (.aif) • Waveform Audio Format (WAV) (.wav)
<p>Digital video data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPEG-4 (.mp4) • motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2) 	
<p>Documentation and scripts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich Text Format (.rtf), PDF/A or PDF (.pdf), HTML (.htm), OpenDocument Text (.odt) • RDF format, e.g. turtle, jsonld 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plain text (.txt) • Some widely-used proprietary formats, e.g. MS Word (.doc/.docx) or MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx) • XML marked-up text (.xml) according to an

		appropriate DTD or schema, e.g. XHTML 1.0
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Table 3. Overview of possible controlled vocabularies to use.

Domain	Controlled Vocabulary	URL
Taxonomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) - NCBI Taxonomy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.marinespecies.org/ - https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy
Geography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marine Regions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.marineregions.org/
Environmental terms, habitat terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Environment Ontology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://sites.google.com/site/environmentontology/home
Measurements and genomics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) - MiXS standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R03/current/ - https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/
Instruments and devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/
People and Institutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ORCID - ROR - EDMO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://orcid.org/ - https://ror.org/ - https://edmo.seadatanet.org/

General ontology search and keywords	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ontobee - OLS - EU Vocabularies - GCMD Vocabularies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://ontobee.org/ - https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4 - https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/controlled-vocabularies - https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn/find-data/idn/gcmd-keywords
General terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO formats (date, time, country) - schema.org - Numerous W3C standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.iso.org/popular-standards.html - https://schema.org - https://www.w3.org/
Master reference lists (Fisheries related)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO formats (country) - Fishing/vessel gear - Fish taxonomy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://vocab.ices.dk/

Table 4. Potential data repositories for redistribution of the thematic data types within AQUASERV.

Thematic data-type category		Research domains	Potential data repositories for redistribution	URLs
Biological	Biodiversity	biogeographic research, species traits, taxonomy	European Ocean Biogeographic Information System (EurOBIS)	www.eurobis.org
			Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS)	www.iobis.org

			Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	http://www.gbif.org
			Biology Portal of the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet Biology)	www.emodnet.eu/biology
			World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS)	www.marinespecies.org
			Morphobank.org	www.morphobank.org
	Genomic	sequencing (DNA, RNA), annotation of features, protein structural information, gene expression profiles, alignment data, chromosomal mapping, phylogenetic trees, Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs), functional genomics, metabolomics, proteomics, environmental DNA	European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena
			GenBank	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/
			DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ)	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/
			dbSNP	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp
			European Variation Archive (EVA)	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva/
			dbVar	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/dbvar
			Database of Genomic Variants Archive (DGVa)	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/dgva

			EBI Metagenomics	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/
			NCBI Trace Archive	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/home/
			NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA)	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra
			NCBI Assembly	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/assembly
			NCBI Reference Sequence Database (RefSeq)	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq/
			Entrez Nucleotide	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide
			UniGene	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/unigene
			HomoloGene	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/homologene
			Protein Information Resource (PIR)	https://pir.georgetown.edu/
			Protein Data Bank (PDB)	https://www ww pdb.org
			UniProt	www.uniprot.org
			Entrez Protein	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/protein

			Protein Circular Dichroism Data Bank (PCDDB)	pcddb.cryst.bbk.ac.uk/home.php
			ArrayExpress	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress/
			Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/
			GenomeRNAi	www.genomernai.org
			dbGAP	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gap
			The European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA)	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ega/
			Database of Interacting Proteins (DIP)	http://dip.doe-mbi.ucla.edu/dip/Main.cgi
			IntAct	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/intact/
			Japanese Genotype-phenotype Archive (JGA)	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/jga
			Biological General Repository for Interaction Datasets	https://thebiogrid.org

			NCBI PubChem BioAssay	https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov
			MetaboLights	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/
			PeptideAtlas	http://www.peptideatlas.org
			PRIDE	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/archive/
			ProteomeXchange	www.proteomexchange.org
	Imaging	zooscan images, flowcam images, flow cytometry images, VPR videos	EcoTaxa	ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr
			FlowRepository	flowrepository.org
	Biogeochemical	biochemical pathways, nutrients	Data Exchange Portal of MPI	https://www.bgc-jena.mpg.de/geodb/projects/Home.php
	Experimental	data resulting from lab experiments		
Oceanographical	Physical	seawater temperature, salinity, ocean currents, waves, geospatial	The Physical Portal of the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet Physics)	www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/
	Chemical	pollution, heavy metals	The Chemical Portal of the European Marine Observation and Data	www.emodnet-chemistry.eu/welcome

			Network (EMODnet Chemistry)	
Climatological	Meteorological	air temperature, wind speed, ...		
	Modelling	climate models	BioModels Database	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bio-models-main/
			Kinetic Models of Biological Systems (KiMoSys)	https://kimosys.org
Technical	Instrumental	experimental instruments, laboratory set-ups		

Table 5. Overview of the thematic data type categories generated within the research domains of AQUASERV. For each data-type category, the common data formats and file types are listed.

	Thematic data type category	Research domains	Data formats	Data file types
Biological	Biodiversity	biogeographic research, species traits, taxonomy	Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A), OBIS-ENV-DATA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative tabular data, minimal metadata: .csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods Quantitative tabular data, extensive metadata: .por; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta Qualitative data: .xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx;

				proprietary/software-specific formats, e.g. NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
Genomic	sequencing (DNA, RNA), annotation of features, protein structural information, gene expression profiles, alignment data, chromosomal mapping, phylogenetic trees, Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs), functional genomics, Metabolomics, Proteomics, environmental DNA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M2B3 Reporting Standard • Read data: general (CRAM, BAM, Fastq) and platform specific (SFF, PacBio, Oxford Nanopore, CompleteGenomics) • Assembled and annotated sequence data: flat file format (FASTA, XML), Multiple Sequence Alignment (MSA) formats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative tabular data, minimal metadata: .csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods • Quantitative tabular data, extensive metadata: .por; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta • Qualitative data: .xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; proprietary/software-specific formats, e.g. NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti 	
Imaging	zooscan images, flowcam images, flow cytometry images, VPR videos, photogrammetry		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg), TIFF (.tif, .tiff), Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF) (.pdf), standard applicable RAW image format (.raw), Photoshop files (.psd), MPEG-4 (.mp4), motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2) • Photogrammetry image and video: .bmp; .NEE; .CR2; .ORF; .avi; .wmv; .mp4; .mpg • Photogrammetry models: STL; OBJ; FBX; COLLADA; 3DS; VRML/X3D • COLLADA; 3DS; VRML/X3D 	

	Biogeochemical	biochemical pathways, nutrients		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative tabular data, minimal metadata: .csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods Quantitative tabular data, extensive metadata: .por; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta Qualitative data: .xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; proprietary/software-specific formats, e.g. NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
	Experimental	data resulting from lab experiments		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative tabular data, minimal metadata: .csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods Quantitative tabular data, extensive metadata: .por; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta Qualitative data: .xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; proprietary/software-specific formats, e.g. NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
Oceanographic	Physical	seawater temperature, salinity, ocean currents, waves, geospatial	NetCDF, Ocean Data View (ODV) format, ASW86	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative tabular data, minimal metadata: .csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods Quantitative tabular data, extensive metadata: .por; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta Qualitative data: .xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; proprietary/software-specific formats, e.g. NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
	Chemical	pollution, heavy metals	NetCDF, Ocean Data View (ODV) format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative tabular data, minimal metadata: .csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative tabular data, extensive metadata: .por; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta Qualitative data: .xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; proprietary/software-specific formats, e.g. NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
Climatological	Meteorological	air temperature, wind speed,...		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative tabular data, minimal metadata: .csv; .tab; .xls; .xlsx; .txt; .mdb; .accdb; .dbf; .ods Quantitative tabular data, extensive metadata: .por; SPSS, Stata, Sas, DDI XML, .sav; .dta Qualitative data: .xml; .rtf; .txt; .html; .doc; .docx; proprietary/software-specific formats, e.g. NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
	Modelling data	climate models		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geospatial data (vector and raster data): .shp; .shx; .dbf; .prj; .sbx; .sbn; .tif; .tfw; .dwg; tabular GIS attribute data; .mdb; .mif; .kml; .ai; .dxf; .svg; binary formats of GIS and CAD packages
Technical	Instrumentation	experimental instruments, laboratory set-ups	images, technical drawings, documentation, spreadsheets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative and qualitative data: .doc(x); .pdf; .xml; .csv Images, technical drawings: JPEG; TIFF; .pdf;